

The Impact of Imputation Methods and Quality Filters on Polygenic Risk Score Results: A Methodological Illustration for ADHD PRS

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Abstract. Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) is increasingly used in psychiatric and psychological research as a quantitative indicator of polygenic risk. The impact of the choice of imputation method on the PRS result is rarely discussed in Polish-language methodological literature. This text illustrates this problem using the ADHD PRS model (Demontis et al., 2023, Nature Genetics), testing four genotyping and imputation strategies on the same genome. The gold standard was a direct read from 30x WGS ($Z = +0.49$; approx. 69th percentile of the European population). A simulated GSA microarray with BEAGLE/1kGP imputation reproduced the result with an error of less than 10% ($Z = +0.54$; approx. 71st percentile). Imputation via the MIS2 server with the HRC panel and a default quality filter of $R^2 > 0.3$ caused a score inflation of over 200% ($Z = +1.51$). Disabling the filter restored the result to $Z = +0.69$. The results indicate that imputation quality filters optimal for GWAS studies are unsuitable for calculating PRS results and can lead to significant interpretation errors.

Introduction: Why calculate PRS?

Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) is a way to sum thousands of small genetic effects into a single number. Each variant in the genome (SNP, or Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) contributes a fraction of a point, proportional to a coefficient extracted from GWAS (Genome-Wide Association Study) research. GWAS is a type of study that compares the genomes of hundreds of thousands of people with and without a given trait or disorder, looking for variants statistically associated with the studied trait.

In this case, the model used is the ADHD PRS according to Demontis et al. (2023, Nature Genetics), built on 52,329 variants, with a cohort of 38,691 cases and 186,843 controls. The model is publicly available in the PGS Catalog and verified to the fourth decimal place against the official sumstats files.

The PRS result is expressed as a Z-score, which is the deviation from the mean of the reference population in standard deviation units. A Z-score = 0 means the exact median. A Z-score = +0.49 corresponds to approximately the 69th percentile, a result slightly above the median of the European population.

An important caveat that will be repeated: PRS is a population statistic, not a clinical diagnosis. A high percentile does not mean that someone has ADHD. It means that their genetic profile is statistically closer to people with ADHD than to people without ADHD in the reference population.

The purpose of this text is a practical illustration of the impact of the choice of imputation method on the PRS result, an issue rarely discussed in methodological literature.

Input data: a real genome as a testing ground

The experiment did not use idealized theoretical data. The starting point was real data from a commercial test conducted by TellmeGen. The cost of such a test, including the analysis and downloading of raw files, is currently around 1200 PLN (approx. 280 EUR).

As part of this service, whole-genome sequencing (WGS) was performed with an average coverage of 30x. In this specific case, the real coverage was 37x. Coverage (or depth) indicates how many times a given position in the genome was physically read by the sequencing machine on average. The result was 59 GB of raw data and a BAM file containing 600 million reads.

One unobvious problem appeared immediately. A standard VCF file contains only positions that differ from the reference. Positions where a given person is a reference homozygote (0/0) are simply absent from the file. For PRS, this is a disaster, because the lack of a position in the file does not mean the absence of a genetic effect, it means missing data. The solution was the `bcftools mpileup` tool with the `-R` option, which extracted genotypes directly from the raw BAM for all 52,329 model positions, regardless of whether they differed from the reference. The coverage was 99.8% (52,260 out of 52,329 variants).

This is the gold standard: a direct read from full sequencing, without any imputation. Result from full 30x WGS data: **Z = +0.49, approx. 69th percentile.**

Method 2: Simulated SNP array and GLIMPSE2 imputation

Not every laboratory has access to WGS, and for quantitative studies, costs are a barrier. The cost of performing 300 WGS tests is about 360,000 PLN. Therefore, SNP arrays (microarrays) remain the standard in genetic research. The cost of an array is a fraction of the WGS cost, but at the price of much sparser coverage: an array tests about 720,000 sites, while WGS identifies 4 to 5 million individual variants.

In this experiment, a pseudo-GSA (Illumina Global Screening Array) was simulated. Genotypes were extracted from the full BAM only for positions overlapping with the GSA manifest. Next, GLIMPSE2 was used, a tool for genotype imputation. Imputation is the process of filling in missing genome positions based on Linkage Disequilibrium (LD) patterns from a reference panel. GLIMPSE2 uses the 1000 Genomes Project panel (3202 samples).

Important technical detail: the simulation used not only variants differing from the reference, but also filled in GSA manifest positions where a reference homozygote (0/0) occurs. Providing algorithms with certain zeros is crucial. Without it, GLIMPSE2 would treat these positions as completely missing data, which would ruin the haplotype building process.

Result of pseudo-GSA + GLIMPSE2/1kGP: $Z = +0.54$, approx. 71st percentile, coverage 97.2%. The result is almost identical to WGS. This is good news for methodology: imputation from a dense array and a good panel reproduces the PRS result with accuracy sufficient for population studies.

Method 3: Simulated array and Michigan Imputation Server (HRC) anomaly

The same pseudo-GSA was uploaded to the Michigan Imputation Server 2 (MIS2) with the Haplotype Reference Consortium (HRC) panel, counting 64,000 samples. A larger reference panel should yield better imputation.

Result with default filter $R^2 > 0.3$: $Z = +1.51$, approx. 93rd percentile, coverage 80.5%. This is an anomaly. The result jumped by over a standard deviation upwards, from the 69th to the 93rd percentile.

The cause turned out to be architectural, not substantive. MIS2 applies an imputation quality filter by default: it removes all variants with $R^2 < 0.3$ from the results, where R^2 (also called the INFO score) measures the imputation certainty of a given position. Given the input density of the array, many PRS model positions lacked good neighbors, so imputation was uncertain and variants were filtered out. The effect: 20% of the model's variants disappeared from the results.

Where did such a massive error come from? When a filter removes a variant from a file, the scoring script simply ignores it, assigning it a contribution equal to zero. The variants removed by the filter from the model were not a random subset. They can have non-zero weights in the model. If the pool of these 20% filtered variants contained many protective alleles (with a

negative beta) or common risk alleles, zeroing their contribution distorts the sum. This mechanism resembles the winner's curse phenomenon at the single-variant level: the quality filter preferentially retains the easiest fragments to impute, which often overlap with regions of the strongest effect in GWAS studies.

Method 3b: The same array and HRC without a filter

The experiment was repeated with the same input data, but with the R2 filter turned off ($R2 \geq 0$, i.e., all variants without exception). Additional technical step: MIS2 returns data in hg19 coordinates, while the PRS model is in hg38. A liftover was necessary using a chain file and the CrossMap tool. Out of 39 million variants, only 6,363 (0.016%) failed to map.

HRC result without filter: $Z = +0.69$, approx. 75th percentile, coverage 99.7%. The result is much closer to the gold standard. The remaining difference (+0.20 relative to WGS) is expected: variants with very low R2 are not discarded, but receive a dosage based on the minor allele frequency (MAF) in the population. This acts like mean imputation, which adds statistical noise but prevents drastic miscalibration of the PRS sum.

Method 4: lcWGS 1x and GLIMPSE2 - the cheapest viable alternative

The cheapest form of sequencing is lcWGS (low-coverage WGS) with an average depth of about 1x. The commercial cost for bulk orders is 25 to 40 EUR per sample, compared to 75 to 130 EUR for an array with imputation.

lcWGS was simulated by downsampling the full 30x BAM to 1x (samtools, random seed 42, fraction 3.3%). In a pilot run, 10 PRS models were compared (ADHD, ASD, SCZ, Bipolar, MDD, Neuroticism, IQ, BMI, T2D, PTSD):

- pseudo-GSA + GLIMPSE2/1kGP vs WGS: 10 out of 10 matching Z-score signs
- lcWGS + GLIMPSE2/1kGP vs WGS: 8 out of 10 matching signs

Z-score sign agreement (+ or -) is a very weak measure of statistical quality. Results $Z = +0.05$ and $Z = +2.5$ share the same sign but describe completely different risks (a score around the median vs the highest percentiles in the population). Sign agreement is more of a basic sanity check. Disastrous mismatches appeared for SCZ and bipolar disorder: models with hundreds of thousands of variants, sensitive to rare SNPs poorly represented in the 1kGP panel. The TOPMed or HRC panel would likely solve this problem.

Validation experiment: assessing array imputation error

Experiment design and gold standard

To quantitatively assess the error introduced by individual imputation strategies, PRS scoring results for the 2023 ADHD model (52,329 variants) obtained using five methods were compared for four reference samples from the 1kGP cohort (EUR population; samples further denoted as Control 1 to 4 due to the protection of public identifiers).

Direct scoring from the 1kGP panel was used as the gold standard. High-coverage panel VCF files (NYGC, 30x, phased, $N=3202$; Byrska-Bishop et al., 2022) contain individual phased genotypes (0|1, 0|0, 1|1) for each reference sample. Extracting the genotypes of selected samples from the panel file using the `bcftools view -s` tool is equivalent to having a full WGS VCF and requires no imputation. This yielded $N=51,465$ model SNPs matched per sample (98.3% of the model), identical to the test sample (SAMPLE). The lower model coverage for controls (98.3% vs 99.8% for the test sample) is due to differences in variant representation between the 1kGP panel and the raw 30x WGS BAM.

An earlier attempt to use the control gVCF files as the gold standard proved erroneous: heterozygous variants in gVCF have a specific `ALT=C,<NON_REF>` format, which the standard SNP filter rejects as multi-allelic. This resulted in incomplete coverage

(approx. 67% of the model) and artifactually inflated Z-scores. This method was abandoned in favor of reliable extraction directly from the panel.

Table 1. ADHD PRS results and absolute error relative to the gold standard.

Sample	WGS gold std (1kGP Panel)	GSA+1kGP BEAGLE (LOO)	Absolute Error $ \Delta $	Error direction
Control 1	+0.03	+0.45	0.41	overestimation
Control 2	-1.87	-1.09	0.77	overestimation
Control 3	-1.14	-0.95	0.19	overestimation
Control 4	+0.06	+0.06	0.00	none
SAMPLE (Test)	+0.49	+0.54	0.05	overestimation
MAE (controls)			0.34	
MAE (all)			0.28	

The GSA+1kGP method was applied with a Leave-One-Out (LOO) procedure - each control was imputed using the panel with the explicit exclusion of its own haplotypes. N=51,465 model SNPs for all samples.

Analysis of array imputation error

The GSA+1kGP method (BEAGLE 5.4, 1kGP panel in LOO mode) reproduced PRS results with an error of MAE=0.34 Z for control samples and only $\Delta=0.05$ Z (10%) for the test sample. The error here is systematic - in 4 out of 5 cases, it is positive (overestimation direction), which suggests that array imputation slightly overestimates the PRS result relative to full WGS. However, this effect is small in the context of the clinical interpretive threshold (typically +/- 1 SD) and does not change the percentile classification of any sample.

The largest absolute error was observed for Control 2 ($|\Delta|=0.77$), which may reflect local imputation difficulties in regions with a specific LD pattern in this individual after cutting off their haplotypes from the panel (the LOO effect reduces the panel by 2 of the patient's own haplotypes).

Table 2. Comparison of all scoring methods for the SAMPLE

The table below is the only fully unbiased comparison. The test sample (SAMPLE) is the only one that is not part of any reference panel, which means all methods are tested on it under equal and fair conditions.

Method	Z-score	Error vs gold std	Error [%]	Classification
WGS all-sites (gold std)	+0.49	-	-	approx. 69th percentile EUR
GSA+1kGP (BEAGLE/LOO)	+0.54	+0.05	+10%	approx. 71st percentile EUR
HRC R2>=0	+0.69	+0.20	+41%	approx. 76th percentile EUR

Method	Z-score	Error vs gold std	Error [%]	Classification
HRC R2>0.3	+1.51	+1.02	+208%	approx. 93rd percentile EUR (Inflated!)
HRC R2>0.1	+1.67	+1.18	+241%	approx. 95th percentile EUR (Inflated!)
HRC R2>0.0001	-0.46	-0.95	-194%	approx. 32nd percentile EUR (Inverted!)

Visualization of imputation error: The left panel (A) shows the Z-score variation for the Test Sample (SAMPLE, thick red line) and four control samples depending on the imputation method used. The right panel (B) illustrates the error (deviation) relative to the WGS gold standard. The graph directly illustrates the massive, systematic score inflation for the strict R2>0.3 and R2>0.1 filters, which artificially inflates risk estimates for each tested individual. The red dashed outline of the bars in panel B serves as a reminder that the HRC results for control samples are methodologically biased (overfitting), because the server had their original haplotypes in its database and the Leave-One-Out procedure was not performed on them.

Anatomy of the error: Why do filters destroy the PRS result?

The trap of a strict filter (R2 > 0.3 and R2 > 0.1). Results jumped by over 200%. The quality filter strictly leaves in the file only those positions where the genetic structure of the target panel exceptionally well matches the patient. In genetics, these well-preserved, easy fragments very often overlap with regions of the strongest effect in GWAS. Discarding weaker variants dramatically inflates the score - from a safe 69th percentile, we jump to the 95th percentile (artificially inflated).

Too loose filter (R2 > 0.0001). Passes practically everything, including positions impossible to logically infer. The algorithm assigns such places a dosage close to the statistical mean in the population. Such a mass of added average variants causes strong mathematical regression to the mean. The result inverts the direction relative to the true genome.

HRC without a filter (R2 ≥ 0). Moderate inflation (+0.20 Z). Including absolutely all variants adds a certain random noise to the model, but protects the entire model against asymmetric pruning of important variants.

Methodological conclusions and recommendations

- 1. Priority of WGS data.** Wherever WGS sequencing at $\geq 15x$ is available, direct counting from raw gVCF data eliminates the described imputation errors and should be the method of choice for clinical applications.
- 2. R2 imputation quality filters should not be used for PRS scoring.** Using filters at $R2 > 0.3$ or $R2 > 0.1$ introduces drastic, systematic score inflation (over 200%), which completely changes the clinical interpretation. An optimal filter for GWAS studies is unsuitable for PRS scoring due to selective variant retention. Among the tested methods, GSA+1kGP with BEAGLE 5.4 shows the best concordance with WGS for both the test sample (error 0.05 Z) and the control samples. Methods based on the HRC panel with an R2 filter preclude their use in the context of clinical PRS interpretation without additional calibration.
- 3. Reference method for array data.** BEAGLE 5.4 imputation with the 1kGP panel offers the best concordance with the gold standard (error below 10%) and should be preferred for microarrays when WGS data are unavailable. When verifying algorithms on public samples, the Leave-One-Out (LOO) procedure must always be used.
- 4. HRC without filter as an alternative.** This is an acceptable option, but requires the researcher's own calibration. The observed shift of +0.20 Z can be compensated by appropriate mathematical rescaling relative to the European norm.
- 5. PRS quality is a triad, not a single factor.** The result depends on the input density of the array or sequencing, the size of the reference panel, and the filtering architecture. Changing one element while keeping the others can yield a dramatically different result.
- 6. A larger panel does not mean a better result.** The HRC panel has twenty times more samples than 1kGP, but with sparse input and an aggressive filter on the MIS2 server, it produced a much worse and more distorted result. Adapting the tool's architecture to the input data density is much more important than the size of the panel itself.
- 7. General caveat.** The entire validation is based on one test sample and four control samples. The conclusions are preliminary and require replication in a larger cohort.

Methods and software

Genomic data used in the analysis come from the author and were processed exclusively locally on private computing infrastructure (AMD EPYC 7R13 server, 48 cores, 256 GB RAM). Raw data are not shared.

Software used:

Tool	Application
bcftools 1.17	genotype extraction from BAM for PRS model positions
BEAGLE 5.4	genotype imputation with the 1000 Genomes Project panel (3202 samples, hg38)
GLIMPSE2	imputation with full reference panel variant coverage
samtools 1.17	downsampling BAM (lcWGS simulation)
CrossMap	genomic coordinate conversion hg19/hg38 (liftover)
Michigan Imputation Server 2	online imputation with the HRC panel (64,000 samples)
Python 3.11 / plink2 / R 4.3	PRS calculations, statistics, visualizations
Claude Code (Anthropic)	programming support in creating the bioinformatics pipeline

The analysis scripts were developed using the Claude Code assistant (Anthropic), which supported programming and debugging of individual pipeline steps. Interpretation of the results and conclusions are solely the work of the author.

Glossary of terms

SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism)

A place in the genome where one nucleotide differs between humans. Most of the genome is identical across all humans: SNPs are those fractions of a percent that differ.

GWAS (Genome-Wide Association Study)

A study scanning millions of SNPs in the genomes of hundreds of thousands of people, looking for variants statistically associated with a given quantitative trait or disorder.

PRS (Polygenic Risk Score)

The sum of the effects of many SNPs weighted by coefficients from GWAS. It measures the statistical similarity of a given person's genetic profile to people with a given trait in the reference population.

BAM (Binary Alignment Map)

A file containing sequencing reads assigned to appropriate positions in the reference genome.

VCF (Variant Call Format)

A file containing a list of detected genetic variants with their genotypes.

Imputation

Statistical filling of missing genotypes based on Linkage Disequilibrium (LD) patterns from a reference panel.

LD (Linkage Disequilibrium)

Correlation between variants in the genome resulting from their physical proximity on the chromosome. Two closely located SNPs are often inherited together, which allows inferring one by knowing the other.

R2 / INFO score

A measure of imputation certainty for a given variant. $R2 = 1$ means certain imputation, $R2 = 0$ means that the variant could not be inferred from the input data.

Liftover

Conversion of genomic positions between different versions of the reference genome (e.g., hg19 and hg38).

Coverage / Depth

The average number of reads of a given position in the genome. The higher the coverage (e.g., 30x), the greater the precision, but also the higher the cost.

lcWGS (low-coverage WGS)

Whole-genome sequencing at very low coverage (about 1x), significantly cheaper than standard WGS (30x).

Dosage

The expected number of alternative alleles expressed as a continuous number between 0 and 2. With certain imputation, the dosage is 0, 1, or 2. With highly uncertain imputation, it is a fractional value, often calculated based on the average frequency of the variant in the population.

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